

DESCRIBING GENDER IN ENGLISH.**Abdullayeva Dildoraxon Obidjon qizi**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7886105>**Key words:** gender, participants, study, demographics, variable**Abstract**

The gender of participants is a common theme in the social sciences when it comes to demographic presentations and quantitative study outcomes. Although it is not a binary variable, gender is sometimes represented by a dichotomous variable with the possible responses of woman/man or female/male. Yet, the definition of gender is rarely given. In this article, we break down the idea of "gender" into its various components and make the case that the researcher must decide whether gender-related factors are pertinent to their particular research issue. To demonstrate how difficult this issue is, we provide a full exposition of factors the researcher should take into account while writing questions concerning each aspect. We also remind the researcher that gender is not a binary category and talk about the difficulties in striking a balance between accounting for the gender variety that already exists while still classifying individuals into gender categories that are useful for statistical analyses. We offer an empirical illustration of how gender identity may be categorized when employing a free-text answer to assist in this process. Last but not least, we propose that additional variables besides participant gender might be more accurate predictors of the outcome variable.

In the social sciences, gender is related to many quantitative study findings and demographics, but what is gender and how can it be operationalized? Researchers try to create reliable instruments with little measurement errors for the majority of variables. In spite of the fact that gender is not a binary category (Ansara & Hegarty, 2014; Hyde, Bigler, Joel, Tate, & van Anders, 2019; Richards et al., 2016), gender measurements are common in most fields of social research (Westbrook & Saperstein, 2015). Few scholars contend, in contrast, that age is best assessed using the two response options "young" and "old," yet gender is still most frequently assessed as a dichotomous variable. There are two issues with the binary gender paradigm. According to Frohard-Dourlent, Dobson, Clark, Doull, and Saewyc (2017), considering gender as a categorical variable without operationalization increases the likelihood of measurement errors. For instance, binary systems do not capture the diversity of gender identities. Response options indicate that conventional measures do not take into account findings relating to identities other than the traditional

genders of man and woman. The worst result of this is erroneous or at least distorted research findings. Second, having gender as a variable with only two possible answers is an unfair practice that disadvantages people who do not identify with either of those possibilities (Nowakowski, Sumerau, & Mathers, 2016). Without facing prejudice in research, a person should be able to determine their gender identity for themselves. Because of this, using a binary gender categorization creates moral dilemmas (Frohard-Dourlent et al., 2017). Several aspects of the gender variable should be considered in order to comprehend how and why attitudes, behaviors, and health outcome variables are influenced by gender. Yet, gender is frequently taken into account in analyses without a conscious consideration of why. For instance, it is challenging to comprehend how gender variations in health—presented as differences between "women" and "men"—are created and sustained since the scientific assessment of gender lacks precision (as discussed by Hart, Saperstein, Magliozzi, & Westbrook, 2019). More often than not, gender is operationalized as a binary system that divides people into either females or males. Moreover, few researchers indicate how this data was used when gender distributions among participants are reported in the methods section.

We add to the growing body of researchers who have emphasized the significance of updating gender-specific demographic questions (Ansara & Hegarty, 2014; Broussard, Warner, & Pope, 2018; Fraser, 2018; Frohard-Dourlent et al., 2017; Hughes, Camden, & Yangchen, 2016; Hyde et al., 2019; Magliozzi, Saperstein, & Westbrook, 2016; Reisner et al. In this essay, we define gender in great detail and go over how to operationalize the gender variable or variables for study. How does gender factor into the research question, if at all?

Describe gender. An examination of the idea

Gender definition is both extremely important and difficult. Hegarty (2001) recommends that in order to deconstruct the gender idea, the quantitative researcher should approach this definition from a performative standpoint. This makes gender a non-essential characteristic that is frequently used according to societal norms conducted (Morgenroth & Ryan, 2018). Quantitative study could support persuasive arguments because the division of gender is "culturally and historically distinctive, internally contradictory, and subject to change" (Hegarty, Ansara, & Barker, 2018, p. 59). (Hegarty & Pratto, 2004). When gender is considered as a binary category in the social sciences, for instance, gender is constructed as a binary category (Morgenroth & Ryan, 2018). Every time a researcher creates a question or item in a survey or questionnaire

that asks about gender, this performance is finished. Because the idea of gender as binary is maintained, the variable is evaluated as a dichotomous one with just two (mutually exclusive) response alternatives. Instead, we propose operationalizing gender as made up of a number of aspects, which can be further broken down into four main facets: (a) physiological/ bodily aspects (sex); (b) gender identity or self-defined gender; (c) legal gender; and (d) social gender in terms of norm-related behaviors and gender expressions (APA, 2015). Due to influences from society and other factors, these aspects may alter over the course of a lifetime (Reisner et al., 2015). Other researchers concentrate on the interactions between these factors (Moerman & van Mens-verhulst, 2004).

The term "transgender" is used to describe people whose assigned gender at birth does not match their self-described gender identity in addition to these aspects (Thanem, 2011). Those who identify as transgender can do so within, outside, or beyond the conventional woman/man binary. In contrast, the term "cisgender" refers to people whose gender identity as assigned at birth matches that (Frohard-Dourlent et al., 2017; van Anders, Caverly, & Johns, 2014).

The term "cisgenderism" refers to the notion that a person's gender identification may be visually discerned or inferred from their appearance (Ansara & Hegarty, 2013, 2014). These presumptions suggest a prejudiced mindset that undermines people's own self-designated because it is believed that physical traits and gender identity are connected (Ansara & Hegarty, 2014). Cisgenderism also affects how well a binary gender system with two distinct, biologically determined genders functions (Hyde et al., 2019). According to Westbrook and Saperstein (2015), researchers will occasionally divide their subjects into gender categories based solely on how they seem, such as woman/man or female/female. The belief that sex and gender are aligned is known as cisnormativity, and it includes the underlying presumption that all women have biological characteristics associated with a female sex, such as a vagina. Although it is assumed that all males have physical characteristics of the male sex, such as a penis (Geist, Reynolds, & Gaytán, 2017). This article aims to demonstrate how cisgenderism and cisnormativity are not based in science. Finally, researchers must consider if gender is significant for their study topics, regardless matter how complex the sex/gender trait is. According to Hyde's gender likeness hypothesis, which is based on meta-analyses, women and men share many psychological traits.

In general, perspectives are similar and not dissimilar. This claim contests the usefulness of gender as a variable or prediction in social sciences. The

gender of the participants may then not necessarily be important. And if gender is to be considered, comparing the disparities between men and women alone is insufficient (Nowatzki & Grant, 2011). Therefore, while conducting studies, researchers should carefully assess whether features of gender are significant to their research topic and how to operationalize these (Reisner et al., 2015).

Body parts and the mixing of sex and gender

The concepts "sex" and "gender" are muddled on a language level as well as theoretically. In English, physical characteristics such as genitalia, chromosomes, and other biological features are frequently referred to as sex, physiological characteristics, while social aspects—including cultural connotations attached to behavior, attitude, and expressions often classified as feminine or masculine—are referred to as gender (Frohard-Dourlent et al., 2017; West & Zimmerman, 1987) (Reisner et al., 2015). Despite this confusion, sex appears to be a poor substitute for gender because it is false to believe that sex precedes and defines gender (Bittner & Goodyear-Grant, 2017; Butler, 1990; Fausto-Sterling, 2012; Westbrook & Westbrook, 2017). As a result, many people with different experiences and/or identities are left out of the conflation because it is normative. Therefore, some academics advocate combining the terms "gender" and "sex" to dispel the notion that sex is an objective category or an objective biological phenomenon (van Anders et al., 2014). Female and male are the traditional dichotomous response choices for "sex," whereas feminine and masculine or woman and man are the typical dichotomous response possibilities for "gender" (Ansara & Hegarty, 2014; Westbrook & Saperstein, 2015). Yet, the question "gender" with the choices "male/female" is the one that is most frequently asked in social science research (Westbrook & Saperstein, 2015). This is an example of how language is used by academics and people in general to make implicit assumptions that confuse sex with gender. So, when a question about gender offers the options "female" or "male" as answers, it is unclear to participants whether the researchers are interested in participants' responses to physical characteristics, legal gender, or self-declared gender identity.

When sex and gender are combined, a binary gender system is also implied, both implicitly and overtly, in which there are only two possible answers and existent variance is ignored (Westbrook & Saperstein, 2015). According to contemporary medical conventions, some people (commonly referred to as having intersex variants) have anatomies that do not fit the normal female/male dichotomy (Lundberg, 2017; Roen, 2019), and as a result, they also defy the traditional sex binary (Nowatzki & Grant, 2011; Richards et

al., 2016). We advise inquiring about bodily/physiological elements specifically when they are pertinent to the study subject. The participant's menstrual cycle may be of interest to the researcher. If this is the case, menstruation should be evaluated rather than asking participants about their sex or gender and assuming that all "women" or even "females" menstruate.

Independent gender identity

Self-defined identity, which can be more or less flexible or change across time and settings, is one significant aspect of gender. While for some persons gender identity remains constant over the course of their lives and in different contexts, for others it changes over time or in different contexts in daily life. The subject of gender identity can be asked in a variety of ways to allow for this internal diversity and fluency. Some people advise asking the question as "How do you now identify?" (2013) Tate, Ledbetter, and Youssef.

Regardless of how the question is worded, quantitative research demands answers that can be categorized. The phrases woman/man are more flexible and can relate to a person's self-defined gender identity independent of their physical characteristics and the gender that was assigned to them at birth, in contrast to the answer categories female/male. As a result, a trans woman, for instance, would feel more at ease and self-assured if the response alternatives are listed as woman/man rather than female/male, particularly if she does not possess all the physical characteristics that are typically associated with the description of "female." Therefore, it is not appropriate to use the terms woman and man interchangeably when referring to genders (Ansara & Hegarty, 2014). Nonetheless, two response options continue to misrepresent gender as binary, with the options woman and male being mutually exclusive (Richards et al., 2016; Westbrook & Saperstein, 2015). A binary system eliminates any those who identify outside of the "conventional" gender binary, who have a fluid gender identity, or who do not identify with gender in any way because there are so many other gender identities (Nowatzki & Grant, 2011). Although the method of binary responses may seem impartial, it is ignoring people with non-binary or fluid gender identities that fall outside or in between the binary categories of woman and male. So, it is possible to identify a non-binary gender identity as being under the general category of "transgender" (Thanem, 2011). Non-binary identity holders do not, however, all identify as transgender.

Gender identity

The social sciences rarely take gender expression into account, which is another facet of gender. Asking participants how they view themselves and how

they think others see them in terms of femininity and masculinity is a quick and easy technique to gauge how participants express their gender (Magliozzi et al., 2016). Moreover, in order to take into consideration individual variety, all participants—regardless of their gender identity—should provide answers to the questions about femininity and masculinity. The Multi-Gender Identity Questionnaire (Multi GIQ; Joel, Tarrasch, Berman, Mukamel, & Ziv, 2014), which is covered in greater depth below, is one of the validated instruments that can also be employed. In terms of social gender norms, such as standards of behavior and appearance, gender expression is also linked to these standards. Gender norms change over time and in different contexts, so it could be challenging to create goods that are precisely about expressions. Others include asking broader questions regarding gender norms in a more general sense. The researcher could specify the precise context of interest and inquire about the participants' attitudes about gender norms within that setting. For instance, there are different standards for women's gender expression in heterosexual and homosexual settings (Huxley, Clarke, & Halliwell, 2014). The researcher could do a prestudy that explicitly identifies the gender norms in the pertinent setting and use these norms when they develop their research questions in order to validate gender norms.

Lawful gender

The majority of societies classify newborns as male or female based primarily on a visual examination of their genitalia (Fausto Sterling, Coll, & Lamarre, 2012). This process establishes the newborn's legal gender, often known as the "assigned gender at birth," which is evident in documents like birth certificates and passports. It's not necessary for people to identify or express themselves according to the gender given to them at birth. Individuals with a physical variation often known as intersex are nevertheless most frequently given one of the binary genders at birth, despite the fact that the bodily variance is substantially larger (Lundberg, 2017). There are currently only a few number of nations (such as Australia, India, New Zealand).

Legal gender is frequently used in official statistics to evaluate gender inequalities, for instance when addressing potential structural disadvantages in pay, health, or other areas. One way to operationalize gender is through legal gender, which has the benefit of being practical. Legal gender is recorded in official and public statistics, making it simple to examine how pertinent metrics differ due to gender without having to gather such data from the general population. Importantly, legal gender can highlight gender inequalities in society

(mainly between males and women). Yet, because gender is not a binary variable and legal gender is not the best proxy for gender identity, it is an imperfect measurement that does not account for gender variation. However, a lot of genderqueer people don't change their legal gender. Hence, supposedly "representative" data are not, in reality, representative (Nowakowski et al., 2016). Notwithstanding the fact that there are still fewer legal genders than woman and man, including more legal genders would be preferable. Some studies advise incorporating two questions about assigned gender at birth and legal gender today rather than just one question about legal gender (Frohard-Dourlent et al., 2017; Magliozzi et al., 2016; Reisner et al., 2015; Tate et al., 2013). This method has the benefit of acknowledging (binary) trans experiences. Others only advocate for these actions when they are pertinent to the research subject (Ansara & Hegarty, 2014). But this technique continues to subtly treat gender as a binary category (except for those nationalities where a third legal gender exist).

Conclusion

Many studies in the social sciences focus on participant gender. Gender analysis is crucial, but it's important to pay closer attention to how gender is operationalized. To do this, we broke down the idea of "gender" into four components: physical characteristics, self-declared gender identity, legal gender, and gender expression (which includes social norms relating to dress and behavior). Our advice is that the researcher should take into account the idea of gender from all of these angles, identify pertinent gender-related characteristics, and add pertinent questions to evaluate these specific characteristics. We have talked about a variety of solutions to help in this process.

The research topic must be the deciding factor in how to evaluate gender. Most commonly, social scientists are interested in how people identify or express themselves from a social perspective rather than the physiological/bodily components of gender (such as genitalia, chromosomes, or physical characteristics). Even after identifying the pertinent factors, asking participants about their gender is a challenging task. We addressed this intricacy in this essay and spoke about how gender-related questions could be more precise based on the components of gender they are trying to measure.

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